

THE IMPACT OF SEEDING DENSITY AND NITROGEN RATES ON FORAGE YIELD AND QUALITY OF AVENA SATIVAL

Ubaid ur Rehman^{*1}, Muhammad Ibrahim², Ali Bakhsh³, Nureen Rafeeq⁴, Jahanzaib⁵,
Muhammad Arham Rayan⁶, Muhammad Imran Akram⁷, Muhammad Tanees Chaudhary⁸,
Hafiza Ruqia Maqsood⁹, Mashal Rehman¹⁰

^{*1,2}Department of Agronomy, Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan 32200, Pakistan

³Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan 32200, Pakistan

⁴Department of Agronomy, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan 60800, Pakistan

^{5,6}Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Bahawalpur 63100, Pakistan

⁷Regional Agricultural Research Institute, Bahawalpur 63100, Pakistan

⁸Cotton Research Station, Vehari 61100, Pakistan

⁹Department of Soil and Environmental Sciences, Muhammad Nawaz Sharif University of Agriculture, Multan 60000, Pakistan

¹⁰Agricultural Research Station, Bahawalpur 63100, Pakistan

^{*}ubaidrehman@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17060767>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 12 June 2025

Accepted: 22 August 2025

Published: 05 September 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Ubaid Ur Rehman

Abstract

Green forage is a vital feed source for livestock, supporting milk, butter, and other dairy products that contribute significantly to human nutrition. In Pakistan, livestock accounts for about 11.39% of GDP and 58.33% of agricultural output. However, during winter, animals often face fodder shortages that reduce milk yield. Oat (*Avena sativa* L.) is the main winter forage, but its production is hampered by factors such as poor soil fertility, especially nitrogen deficiency, low organic matter, and suboptimal management. This study evaluated the effect of three seed rates (70, 80, and 90 kg ha⁻¹) and five nitrogen levels (0–160 kg ha⁻¹) on oat forage yield and quality. Results showed that the highest forage yield (54.67 t ha⁻¹) and superior growth traits including plant height, tiller number, leaf area, and biomass were achieved with 90 kg seed rate and 160 kg N ha⁻¹. Nutritional traits such as crude protein (10.54%), crude fiber (31.62%), and ash content (9.39%) were also maximized under this combination. Economic analysis indicated that 90 kg seed rate with 120–160 kg N ha⁻¹ gave the best benefit cost ratio and net returns. Therefore, a seed rate of 90 kg ha⁻¹ with 120 kg N ha⁻¹ is recommended for improved forage yield, quality, and profitability.

INTRODUCTION

Green forage is one of the most affordable and dependable energy sources, providing high-quality feed for livestock. However, maintaining a consistent supply of green fodder remains a major challenge for

sustaining milk, butter, and other dairy-based products for human use [1]. In Pakistan, livestock contributes 58.33% to agriculture and 11.39% to GDP (2016–2017) [2]. Despite its central role, animals are often

undernourished, leading to reduced productivity. Globally, low forage yields are largely attributed to poor soil fertility, limited organic matter, and widespread nitrogen deficiency [3]. Oat (*Avena sativa* L.), locally referred to as “jai” or “jodar,” belongs to the Poaceae family and is a key winter fodder crop in Pakistan, where a 52–54% deficit in domestic forage demand has been reported [4]. Oat is widely grown for both grain and forage and is valued as one of the most economical cereal fodders under irrigated and rainfed conditions. Its forage is highly nutritious, palatable, and succulent, and its feeding value can be further improved by mixing with legumes such as berseem, alfalfa, Persian clover, and pea [5]. Rich in protein, vitamin B1, fat, phosphorus, and iron, oat also provides grains and leaves that serve as a good source of carotene and carbohydrates [6,7]. Oat forage contains around 30.44% crude fiber, 9.3% crude protein, 3.56% fat, and 0.27% phosphorus [7]. The crop performs best in temperate climates, requiring 16–32 °C and approximately 400 mm rainfall, though it shows poor tolerance to waterlogging [1,8]. Despite its potential, oat yields in Pakistan remain below international averages due to unfavorable climatic conditions, soil infertility, lack of improved varieties, limited irrigation, and improper sowing and fertilizer management [9]. Within the genus *Avena*, about seventy species exist, with *Avena byzantina* and *Avena sativa* being the most widely cultivated for fodder purposes [8]. Oat ranks sixth among cereals worldwide, after wheat, maize, rice, barley, and sorghum. It is a multicut forage crop capable of producing high biomass when managed well, with the ideal harvest stage being around 50% flowering [10]. Achieving optimum seed rate is crucial for maintaining sufficient plant population, which directly influences forage yield and quality. Both very low and very high plant populations reduce yield potential and forage value; therefore, seeding density must be carefully managed. When oats are grown in mixtures with legumes, their seed rates are

usually reduced to maintain balance in the stand [11,12]. Previous studies have shown that suboptimal seed rates negatively affect yield and quality [13]. Lower seed rates often increase plant height, while higher seed rates reduce height due to competition for light and nutrients [14]. Kakol et al. [15] observed that a 100 kg ha⁻¹ seed rate resulted in higher green forage yield than 125 kg ha⁻¹, with no significant effect on forage quality. Similarly, Jan and Jan [16] reported nonsignificant differences in forage yield across different seed rates. Abate and Wegi [13] concluded that the combined use of optimum seed rate and fertilizer application had a significant effect on forage yield and dry matter accumulation. Nitrogen (N) is a key component of proteins and other vital compounds required for plant growth and development [17]. It plays an essential role in cell division, tillering, stem elongation, heading, booting, and grain filling [18–21]. As a primary constituent of chlorophyll, amino acids, nucleic acids, and enzymes, N strongly influences crop morphology and productivity. Since nitrogen is the most limiting nutrient in soils, cereals and fodders often require higher external inputs [22]. However, its efficiency is affected by soil pH, moisture, and temperature, which regulate N losses [23]. Therefore, applying the right dose is critical for maximizing yield and forage quality [16]. Earlier studies reported that green fodder yield of oat increased significantly with 80 kg N ha⁻¹ compared to control, 40, or 120 kg ha⁻¹ [24]. Still, the optimum nitrogen requirement varies with agroclimatic conditions and locations. Based on this, the study hypothesized that increasing nitrogen application would significantly enhance forage yield and quality, while seed rate would also exert a strong influence. The findings are expected to help optimize nitrogen use and seeding density for oat production under the agroclimatic conditions of Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan.

Materials and Methods

The present field experiment aimed at optimizing seed rate and nitrogen fertilization in oat was carried out during the winter season of 2015–2016 at the research farm of Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan. The trial was established on a previously fallow plot that had been leveled and prepared through standard cultivation practices. Prior to sowing, a presowing irrigation of 10 cm depth was applied, followed by two cultivations with a cultivator and subsequent planking once the soil achieved a suitable moisture condition. The oat variety S-2000, recommended for forage purposes, served as the test cultivar. The experiment comprised three seed rates (70, 80, and 90 kg ha⁻¹) in combination with five nitrogen levels (0, 40, 80, 120, and 160 kg ha⁻¹). Sowing was carried out in rows spaced 30 cm apart using a single-row hand drill, with each plot consisting of six rows. Planting took place in the second week of December 2015. Nitrogen and phosphorus were supplied through urea and single superphosphate (SSP), respectively. The full recommended dose of phosphorus (80 kg ha⁻¹) was applied at sowing, whereas nitrogen was split into two equal applications half at planting and the remaining half with the first irrigation. Across the crop cycle, three irrigations were provided. Harvesting was done manually at ground level using a sickle. Observations were recorded following standard procedures, applied consistently across treatments. Parameters studied included germination count (m⁻²), plant height (cm), number of leaves per plant, tiller density (m⁻²), leaf area per tiller (cm²), fresh weight (kg m⁻²), dry weight (g m⁻²), green forage yield (t ha⁻¹), and dry matter yield (t ha⁻¹). Germination counts were obtained by daily monitoring until no further emergence occurred, with the final count used for analysis. Plant height and number of leaves were recorded from five randomly selected plants per plot, while tiller number was also assessed from randomly chosen plants. Fresh biomass was estimated through destructive sampling of a 1 m² area, weighed immediately, and then oven-dried at 70°C to determine dry weight. The results were scaled up to per-hectare values. In addition, forage quality traits including crude protein (%), crude fiber (%), and total ash (%) were determined following standard

laboratory protocols.

An economic appraisal was carried out to assess the profitability of the treatments. Gross and net incomes were computed from the total forage yield, while production costs included both fixed and variable expenses. Benefit-cost was determined by dividing the gross income by the total cost according to the procedures devised by CIMMYT (1988).

Benefit cost ratio= Net income/ Total expenditure

All collected data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Fisher's method. Treatment means were compared at the 5% probability level using the least significant difference (LSD) test [25].

Results and Discussion

Seed rate had a significant influence on the germination of forage oat, whereas nitrogen application levels showed no marked effect (Table 1). Likewise, the interaction between seed rate and nitrogen dose was nonsignificant. The maximum germination count was recorded under S3 (138.77 m⁻²), while the minimum plant population was observed in S1 (108.42 m⁻²) (Table 2). The higher germination achieved at S3 was primarily due to the greater number of seeds sown per unit area. Both seed rate and nitrogen levels, individually as well as in combination, produced significant differences in plant height, leaf number, leaf area per tiller, and biomass accumulation (Table 1). The tallest plants were obtained in treatment S2N5 (122.97 cm), which was statistically comparable with S1N5, S3N5, S3N4, and S1N4. In contrast, the shortest plants were recorded in S2N1 (91.37 cm), S1N2 (94.37 cm), S1N1 (94.43 cm), and S1N3 (96.33 cm). Plant stature showed a consistent increase with each incremental nitrogen dose (Table 2). The greatest number of leaves per plant was observed in S3N5 (24.50), which did not differ significantly from S2N5, S3N4, and S2N4. The lowest values were documented for S2N1, statistically similar to S1N1, S1N2, and S3N1 (Table 2). Leaf area per tiller was also strongly influenced, with S2N5 producing the largest leaf area, closely followed by S3N4, S1N5, S3N2, and S3N5. The smallest leaf areas occurred under S1N1, S1N2, and S1N3 (Table 2). Seed rate and nitrogen levels significantly affected forage yield,

dry matter yield, and quality components such as crude fiber, crude protein, and total ash (Table 3). In general, higher seed rates combined with increased nitrogen enhanced all these parameters. The greatest green forage yield was attained under S3N5, which was statistically similar to S3N4, S2N5, and S2N4 (Table 4). Conversely, the lowest forage yield was recorded for S1N1, which was not significantly different from S2N1 and S3N1. Earlier findings by Kakol et al. (2003) also confirmed the positive response of oat to both seed density and nitrogen fertilization. Shukla and Lal (1998) similarly noted substantial yield improvements with higher nutrient input. For dry matter yield, the highest value was achieved in S1N4, while S1N1 exhibited the minimum (Table 4). Crude fiber percentage was also influenced by treatments, with S3N5 yielding the highest proportion, whereas the lowest was observed in S2N1 (Table 4). The combined effects of seed rate and nitrogen application significantly altered production costs (Table 5) and overall profitability (Table 6). Among the treatments, S3N4 gave the maximum net income and benefit-cost ratio, while S1N1 proved least economical. Although increasing nitrogen generally improved yield-related traits, the economic evaluation suggested that the highest nitrogen level (N5) was not the most profitable option. Although N5 produced better yields and higher returns than lower nitrogen levels, N4 ultimately provided the best balance between cost and benefit, with the highest net income and benefit-cost ratio (Table 6).

A higher germination count was directly associated with the increased seed rate applied. Similar observations were reported by [26], who noted a greater plant population in forage maize when sown at higher seed densities. The nonsignificant influence of nitrogen levels on germination percentage of oat was also confirmed by Shukla and Lal [27], who found no substantial differences when oats were grown under either organic or inorganic fertilization. This indicates that nitrogen contributes more effectively during later stages of plant growth rather than during seed germination. Zahid et al. [28] observed that nitrogen, particularly when combined with farmyard manure, promoted

taller oat plants. Likewise, Irfan et al. [29] documented significant improvements in plant height under nitrogen fertilization, which aligns with reports suggesting that split applications of nitrogen and potassium significantly enhance growth. One study recorded a maximum height of 119.58 cm in forage oat with the application of 80 kg N ha⁻¹.

The greater number of leaves per plant may also be attributed to nitrogen's role in stimulating vegetative growth. Ahmad et al. [30] provided supporting evidence, while Irfan et al. [29] reported that higher nitrogen rates increased leaf numbers compared with lower rates. In terms of tillering, the maximum tiller density was obtained in S3N5, which was statistically comparable to S3N4, S2N5, and S3N3. In contrast, the lowest number of tillers per plant was found in S1N1, closely resembling S2N1, S3N1, and S1N2 (Table 2). Metwally et al. [31] also found that 100 kg N ha⁻¹ markedly improved the tillering capacity of oats, while Jehangir et al. [32] confirmed that soil fertility enhancement positively influenced tiller production. Similarly, Ahmad et al. [30] reported that applying 150 kg N ha⁻¹ together with 60 kg P ha⁻¹ produced the largest leaf area (128 cm²). Jiwang et al. [33] noted a consistent increase in leaf area with rising fertilizer levels, and Khandaker and Islam [34] found that 120 kg N ha⁻¹ maximized leaf area in oats. In maize, Tanha [35] also recorded the greatest leaf expansion at 200 kg N ha⁻¹.

Fresh and dry biomass accumulation also followed the same trend, with increases corresponding to higher seed rates and nitrogen doses. The maximum fresh weight was observed in S3N5, closely followed by S3N4, while the minimum was in S1N1. Sharma and Bhunia [36] compared nutrient sources and found that inorganic nitrogen resulted in the highest fresh biomass per tiller. Similarly, Singh et al. [37] reported that farmyard manure enhanced fodder yield in maize, while Wheed et al. [38] demonstrated that elevated nitrogen improved green forage yield. Orloff et al. [39] achieved the highest dry fodder yield with 136 kg N ha⁻¹, corroborating these findings.

Crude protein content, a key determinant of forage quality, was also strongly influenced by nitrogen. Increasing nitrogen from lower to higher doses elevated crude protein levels, although excessive N tended to reduce overall forage quality by making the crop excessively succulent. The highest crude protein percentage was obtained with S2N5, whereas S2N1 produced the lowest. Kumar et al. [40] showed that 80 kg N ha⁻¹ maximized crude protein yield, while later work by Kumar et al. [41] suggested that levels beyond 80 kg ha⁻¹ provided diminishing returns. Khan et al. [42] explained that nitrogen directly affects crude protein because it is an essential component of proteins, chlorophyll, and protoplasts, a view also supported by Farooq et al. [43]. Similar results were reported in [44], where crude fiber increased with 150 kg N ha⁻¹.

Ash content was likewise affected, with the highest percentage recorded in S3N4 and the lowest in S1N1 (Table 4). Alajmi et al. [45] observed comparable results, reporting maximum ash content with 150 kg N ha⁻¹. Saleh et al. [46] also concluded that nitrogen supplementation significantly raised ash concentration in forage maize.

Overall, the results demonstrated that both seed rate and nitrogen application play critical roles in enhancing yield and forage quality. Based on the findings, cultivation of forage oats with a seed rate of 90 kg ha⁻¹ combined with 120 kg N ha⁻¹ is recommended for achieving higher productivity, improved nutritional quality, and greater economic benefits.

References

- M. F. Iqbal, M. A. Sufyan, M. M. Aziz, I. A. Zahid, Q. Ghani, and S. Aslam, "Efficacy of nitrogen on green fodder yield and quality of oat (*Avena sativa* L.)," *The Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences (Pakistan)*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 82-84.b, 2009.
- H. Karar, M. Amjad Bashir, R. Atalla Alajmi et al., "Farmers' knowledge, perception and management of mango mealy bug, *Drosicha mangiferae* Green (Hemiptera: Monophlebidae), on *Mangifera indica* in Punjab, Pakistan," *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 28, no. 7, pp. 3936-3942, 2021.
- S. J. Ulysses, *Fertilizers and Soil Fertility*, Reston Publishing Co, Reston, Virginia, 2nd edition, 1982.
- B. Bhatti, "Fodder production in rainfed areas of Punjab," in *Fodder Production in Pakistan*, pp. 113-114, PARC. P, 1992.
- E. F. Thomson, S. Rihawi, and N. Nersoyan, "Nutritive value and yields of some forage legumes and barley harvested as immature herbage, hay and straw in northwest Syria," *Experimental Agriculture*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 49-56, 1990.
- A. Hussain, S. Khan, M. U. Mufti, and A. Bakhsh, "Introduction and use of oats cultivars in Pakistan," in *Proceedings of "5th TAPAFON (Temperate Asia Pasture and Fodder Network) meeting/conference held at Renewable Natural Resources Research Center*, pp. 159-166, Bajo (Wangdue-Bhutan), 2002.
- A. R. Chaudhry, *Crop production*, Nation book foundation Islamabad, 1994.
- M. B. Bhatti, A. Hussain, and D. Mohammad, "Fodder production potential of different oat cultivars under two cut system," *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research*, vol. 13, pp. 184-190, 2002.
- M. Ibrahim, "Determining forage production potential of maize sown as a mixture with different legumes under different nitrogen applications. Ph. D. Thesis, Dept. of Agron., Univ. of Agric., Faisalabad, Pakistan".

- A. Alipatra, C. K. Kundu, M. K. Mandal, H. Banerjee, and P. Bandopadhyay, "Yields and quality improvement in fodder oats (*Avena sativa* L.) through split application of fertilizer and cutting management," *Journal of Crop and Weed*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 193-195, 2013.
- A. Basit, M. Farhan, W. D. Mo et al., "Enhancement of resistance by poultry manure and plant hormones (salicylic acid & citric acid) against tobacco mosaic virus," *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 3526-3533, 2021.
- H. Karar, M. Amjad Bashir, A. Khaliq, M. Jaffar Ali, R. Atalla Alajmi, and D. M. Metwally, "Stink bug *Agonoscelis* spp. (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) - An emerging threat for seed production in alfalfa crop (*Medicago sativa* L.) and their successful management," *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 3477-3482, 2021.
- D. Abate and T. Wegi, "Determination of optimum seed and fertilizer rate for fodder oat in Bale Highland Southeastern Ethiopia," *International Journal of Soil and Crop Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 73-76, 2014.
- B. S. Reddy, *Physiological Studies on Oat (Avena sativa) Varieties under Two Cutting Regimes*, M. Sc. (Agri.) Thesis, Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, 1976.
- N. B. Kakol, S. C. Alagundagi, and S. V. Hosamani, "Effect of seed rate and nitrogen levels on forage yield and quality of oat," *Indian Journal of Animal Nutrition*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 149-154, 2003.
- T. Jan and M. T. Jan, "Effect of sowing dates and seed rates on the forage yields of oats," *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture (Pakistan)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 473-476, 1994.
- S. K. Das, K. L. Sharma, N. Sharma, and K. Srinivas, "Soil fertility management and fertilizer use," in *Sustainable Development of Dry Land Agriculture in India*, R. P. Singh, Ed., pp. 95-117, Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur, India, 1995.
- R. A. Olson and D. J. Sander, "Corn production," in *Corn and Corn Improvement*, G. F. Sprague and J. W. Dudley, Eds., pp. 639-686, American Society of Agronomy/Crop Science Society of America/Soil Science Society of America, Madison, 2015.
- F. Zapata and O. V. Cleenput, "Recovery of ¹⁵N-labelled fertilizer by sugar beet? spring wheat and winter rye? sugar beet cropping sequences," *Fertilizer Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 269-278, 1986.
- M. Worku, B. E. Friesen, O. A. Diallob, and W. J. Horst, "Nitrogen uptake and utilization in contrasting nitrogen efficient tropical maize hybrids," *Crop Science*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 519-528, 2007.
- R. A. K. Amanullah and S. K. Khalil, "plant density and nitrogen Effects on Maize phenology and Grain yield," *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 246-260, 2009.
- J. L. Havlin, J. D. Beaton, S. L. Tisdale, and W. L. Nelson, *Soil Fertility and Fertilizers: An Introduction to Nutrient Management*, Pearson Education Inc., India, 6th edition, 1999.
- B. Malakar, S. Mondal, P. Bandopadhyay, and C. K. Kundu, "Response of forage oat to nitrogen and phosphorous fertilizer in the new alluvial zone of West Bengal," *Journal of crop and weed*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 36-38, 2009.
- N. Ratan, U. N. Singhand, and H. C. Pandey, "Yield and quality of oat as influenced by nitrogen and varieties in Bundelkhand region U. P. India," *Agricultural Science Research Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 27-30, 2016.
- R. Singh, B. R. Sood, V. K. Sharma, N. S. Rana, and R. Singh, "Effect of cutting management and nitrogen on forage and seed yields of oat (*Avena sativa* L.)," *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 362-366, 1998.
- M. Ayub, R. Ahmad, M. A. Nadeem, and R. M. A. Khan, "Effect of different levels of nitrogen and seed rates on growth, yield and quality of maize fodder," *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, vol. 40, pp. 140-143, 2003.

N. P. Shukla and M. Lal, "Response of oat (*Avena sativa* L.) to nitrogen in relation to moisture conservation techniques under restricted irrigations," *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 229-232, 1994.

M. S. Zahid, Z. A. Gurmani, M. Imran, and M. Bashir, "Effect of fertilizer dose on yield and yield components of fodder oat under rainfed condition of pothwar region," *J. Agric*, vol. 43, no. 3, 2005.

M. Irfan, M. Ansar, A. Sher, A. Wasaya, and A. Sattar, "Improving forage yield and morphology of oat varieties through various row spacing and nitrogen application," *JAPS: Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 1718- 1724, 2016.

A. H. Ahmad, A. Wahid, F. Khalid, N. Fiaz, and M. S. I. Zamir, "Impact of organic and inorganic sources of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers on growth, yield and quality of forage oat (*Avena sativa* L.)," *Cercetari Agronomic in Moldova*, vol. 44, no. 3, 2011.

D. M. Metwally, S. A. Albasyouni, I. A. H. Barakat et al., "Prevalence rate and molecular characteristics of *Oestrus ovis* L. (Diptera, Oestridae) in sheep and goats from Riyadh, Saudi Arabia," *Animals*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 689, 2021.

I. A. Jehangir, M. H. Khan, F. Rasool et al., "Effect of sowing dates, fertility levels and cutting managements on growth, yield and quality of oats (*Avena sativa* L.)," *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 648-651, 2013.

Z. Jiwang, H. Changhao, W. Kongjun, D. Shuting, and L. Peng, "Effects of plant density on forage nutritive value of whole plant corn," *Agricultural Sciences in China*, vol. 3, no. 11, pp. 842-848, 2004.

Z. H. Khandaker and M. M. Islam, "Effect of nitrogen fertilization and stage of maturity on yield and quality of fodder maize," *Bangladesh Journal of Animal Science (Bangladesh)*, vol. 7, no. 1-2, pp. 47-53, 1988.

I. Y. Tanha, *Yield and Quality Response of Forage Maize as Affected by Different Nitrogen Levels and Seeding Rates*, M. Sc. Thesis, Dept. Agron. Univ. Agric, Faisalabad, Pakistan, 2009.

S. K. Sharma and S. K. Bhunia, "Response of oat to cutting management, method of sowing and nitrogen," *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 563-567, 2001.

V. Singh, J. S. Khokar, Y. P. Joshi, and S. S. Verma, "Effect of nitrogen, seed rates and methods of sowing on forage oat (*Avena sativa* L.)," *Forage Research*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 29-32, 1989.

A. Wheed, W. Ahmad, M. A. Shehzad, and M. Shahid, "Nitrogen and phosphorous impact on forage oat (*Avena sativa* L.) growth, yield and its quality attributes," *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 473-479, 2012.

E. Johansson, M. L. Prieto-Linde, and J. Ö. Jönsson, "Effects of wheat cultivar and nitrogen application on storage protein composition and breadmaking quality," *Cereal Chemistry Journal*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 19-25, 2001.

TABLE 1: Analysis Of Variance Of Different Seeding Rates, Nitrogen Doses, And Their Interactions On Germination Count, Plant Height, Number Of Tillers Per Plant, Leaf Area Per Tiller, And Fresh And Dry Biomass Of Oat.

SOV	DF	SS	MS	Pvalue
Germination count				
Seed rate (S)	2	6932.5	3466.25	0.0000**
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	994.2	248.56	0.0852NS

S×N	8	1168.6	146.08	0.2640NS
Plant height				
Seed rate (S)	2	359.69	179.85	0.0028*
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	4829.57	1207.39	0.000**
S×N	8	569.46	71.18	0.0173*
Number of tillers				
Seed rate (S)	2	9.9613	4.98067	0.0000**
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	25.3444	6.33611	0.0000**
S×N	8	2.5542	0.31928	0.00136*
Leaf area per tiller				
Seed rate (S)	2	1570.23	785.114	0.0000**
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	2863.32	715.831	0.0000**
S×N	8	883.81	110.476	0.0235*
Fresh weight				
Seed rate (S)	2	3.4964	1.74822	0.0000*
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	32.3658	8.09144	0.0000**
S×N	8	0.1969	0.02461	0.0240*
Dry weight				
Seed rate (S)	2	287097	143548	0.0008*
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	7122222	1780555	0.0000**
S×N	8	534114	66764	0.0016*

SOV: source of variation, DF: degree of freedom, SS: sum of squares, MS: mean squares, *: significant, NS: non-significant.

TABLE 2: Interactive Effect Of Seed Rate And Nitrogen Level On Germination Count, Plant Height, Numbers Of Leaves, And Leaf Area Per Tiller Of Forage Oat.

Treatments	Germination count (m ⁻²)	Plant height (cm)	Number of leaves (m ⁻²)	Leaf area per tiller (cm ²)	Fresh weight (kg m ⁻²)	Dry weight (g m ⁻²)
Seed rate (S)						
S ₁	108.42 C	104.45 B	20.180 B	110.08 B	3.8267 C	897.7 B
S ₂	125.19 B	108.1 AB	20.780 B	118.32 A	4.2200 B	845.3 B
S ₃	138.77 A	111.37 A	22.060 A	100.02 C	4.5067 A	1034.7 A
LSD	3.8	1.8	0.32	2.33	0.34	45.13
Nitrogen doses (N)						
N ₁	119.93 NS	92.51 D	19.667 D	107.00 B	2.7889 E	457.6 C
N ₂	118.64	103.48 C	17.756 E	117.81 A	3.7444 D	468.1 C
N ₃	123.08	105.32 C	20.956 C	121.95 A	4.3333 C	1008.9 B
N ₄	128.47	116.71 B	22.756 B	94.91 de	4.9556 B	1342.0 A
N ₅	130.61	121.90 A	23.900 A	96.54 de	5.1000 A	1353.0 A
LSD 0.05	4.91	2.33	0.42	90.54 e	0.44	58.26
S × N						

S ₁ N ₁	109.97 NS	94.43 g	17.50 g	115.91 ab	2.47 k	403.0 e
S ₁ N ₂	103.23	94.37 g	17.67 fg	121.61 a	3.23 h	459.7 e
S ₁ N ₃	101.70	96.33 fg	20.63 d	102.15 cd	4.03 fg	962.7 cd
S ₁ N ₄	115.97	115.70 abc	22.20 c	104.71 cd	4.63 d	1317.3 b
S ₁ N ₅	111.23	121.40 ab	22.90 bc	104.58 cd	4.77 d	1346.0 b
S ₂ N ₁	111.2	91.37 g	17.43 g	115.78 ab	2.87 j	494.0 e
S ₂ N ₂	114.53	104.50 ef	19.10 ef	123.18 a	3.90 g	470.7 e
S ₂ N ₃	129.13	106.30 de	20.03 de	107.38 bc	4.33 e	1167.3 bc
S ₂ N ₄	131.23	115.57 abc	23.03 abc	121.54 a	4.93 c	1016.7 cd
S ₂ N ₅	139.87	122.97 a	24.30 ab	119.88 a	5.07 c	1348.3 b
S ₃ N ₁	138.33	91.73 g	18.33 fg	121.74 a	3.03 i	475.7 e
S ₃ N ₂	138.17	111.57 cde	22.23 c	121.08 a	4.10 f	474.0 e
S ₃ N ₃	138.4	113.33 bcd	22.20 c	10.65	4.63 d	896.7 d
S ₃ N ₄	138.2	118.87 abc	23.03 abc	110.77	5.30 b	1692.0 a
S ₃ N ₅	140.73	121.33 ab	24.50 a		5.47 a	1364.7 b
LSD 0.05	17.44	8.29	1.48		0.16	206.7
Mean	124.13	107.98	21		4.18	19.32

Here, S₁ = 70 kg ha⁻¹, S₂ = 80 kg ha⁻¹, S₃ = 90 kg ha⁻¹, N₁ = 0 kg ha⁻¹, N₂ = 40 kg ha⁻¹, N₃ = 80 kg ha⁻¹, N₄ = 120 kg ha⁻¹, and N₅ = 160 kg ha⁻¹. Means sharing similar letters within a column are statistically nonsignificant.

TABLE 3: Analysis of variance of different seeding rates, nitrogen doses, and their interactions on forage and dry matter yields, crude fiber, crude protein, and total ash of forage oat.

SOV	DF	SS	MS	P value
<i>Forage yield</i>				
Seed rate (S)	2	338.71	169.356	0.0000**
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	3213.35	803.338	0.0000**
S×N	8	28.89	3.612	0.0151*
<i>Dry matter yield</i>				
Seed rate (S)	2	3.7773	1.8887	0.0008*
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	83.3142	20.8286	0.0000**
S×N	8	4.2604	0.5326	0.0268*
<i>Crude protein</i>				
Seed rate (S)	2	1.2379	0.6189	0.0304*
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	72.2770	18.0692	0.0000**
S×N	8	6.8236	0.8529	0.0003*
<i>Crude fiber</i>				
Seed rate (S)	2	53.324	26.6618	0.0037*
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	226.558	56.6395	0.0000**
S×N	8	97.847	12.2309	0.0111*
<i>Total ash</i>				
Seed rate (S)	2	9.3352	4.66760	0.0000**
Nitrogen doses (N)	4	11.2192	2.80480	0.0000**
S×N	8	4.8808	0.61010	0.0029*

TABLE 4: Interactive effect of seed rate and nitrogen level on green forage yield, dry matter yield, crude protein, crude fiber, and total ash of forage oat.

Treatments	Green forage yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Dry matter yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Crude protein (%)	Crude fiber (%)	Total ash (%)
<i>Seed rate (S)</i>					
S ₁	38.827 C	19.07 B	8.87 A	27.28 B	7.58 C
S ₂	42.717 B	19.16 B	8.52 A	27.10 B	7.91 B
S ₃	45.517 A	19.73 A	8.88 B	29.49 A	8.67 A
LSD 0.05	0.4	0.16	0.14	0.72	0.14
<i>Nitrogen doses (N)</i>					
N ₁	28.389 E	17.17 D	6.98 E	24.75 C	7.14 C
N ₂	37.978 D	18.57 C	7.82 D	26.76 B	7.93 B
N ₃	43.983 C	19.40 B	8.72 C	27.36 B	8.30 AB
N ₄	50.170 B	20.64 A	9.86 B	29.88 A	8.44 A
N ₅	51.249 A	20.87 A	10.42 A	31.03 A	8.48 A
LSD 0.05	0.51	0.21	0.19	0.92	0.18
<i>S × N</i>					
S ₁ N ₁	25.833 i	16.60 d	7.45 ef	24.55 d	6.57 e
S ₁ N ₂	32.600 g	18.07 c	8.23 d	24.71d	7.02 e
S ₁ N ₃	41.033 ef	19.33 b	8.41 d	27.75 bcd	8.00 cd
S ₁ N ₄	46.667 c	20.57 a	9.80 bc	29.32 abc	7.88 cd
S ₁ N ₅	48.000 c	20.80 a	10.45 ab	30.05 ab	8.45 bc
S ₂ N ₁	29.000 h	16.70 d	5.94 g	20.55 e	6.78 e
S ₂ N ₂	39.667 f	18.23 c	7.22 f	26.22 cd	7.79 d
S ₂ N ₃	43.917 d	19.43 b	9.27 c	27.15 bcd	8.45 bc
S ₂ N ₄	49.923 b	20.63 a	9.93 abc	30.15 ab	8.05 cd
S ₂ N ₅	51.080 b	20.80 a	10.28 ab	31.42 a	8.49 bc
S ₃ N ₁	30.333 h	18.20 c	7.54 ef	29.15 abc	8.05 cd
S ₃ N ₂	41.667 e	19.37 b	8.00 de	29.35 abc	8.99 ab
S ₃ N ₃	47.000 c	19.43 b	8.49 d	27.18 bcd	8.45 bc
S ₃ N ₄	53.920 a	20.90 a	9.85 bc	30.15 ab	9.39 a
S ₃ N ₅	54.667 a	20.73 a	10.54 a	31.62 a	8.49 bc
LSD 0.05	1.84	0.75	0.66	3.29	0.65
Mean	42.35	19.32	8.76	27.95	8.06

TABLE 5: Fixed and variable costs of production for forage oat.

Operation/input	No. of operations/ha	Rate per unit (PKR)	Cost per unit (PKR)
Land preparation Ploughing	2	2000 ha ⁻¹	4000 ha ⁻¹

Planking	1	1500 ha ⁻¹	1500 ha ⁻¹
Sowing Seed/sowing	*	*	*
Drill sowing		2500 ha ⁻¹	2500 ha ⁻¹
<i>Irrigation</i>			
Irrigation charges	3 irrigations	1000	3000
Labor cost for irrigation	1 man for 3 times	500 per day	1500
<i>Fertilizer</i>			
Nitrogen from urea	*	*	*
Phosphorus from single super phosphate	80 kg	111 kg ¹	8888
Plant protection measures		Weedin g	1000
<i>Harvesting</i>			
Labor charges for harvesting	7 men	500 per men	3500
Land rent	6 months	30250 ha ⁻¹	15125
Total fixed cost			41013
*: variable cost of seed, *: variable cost of nitrogen.			

TABLE 6: Economics analysis for different seed rates and nitrogen doses used to produce forage oat

Treatments	Gross income (PKR ha ⁻¹)	Total cost (PKR ha ⁻¹)	Net income (PKR ha ⁻¹)	Benefit : cost ratio
S ₁ N ₁	51666	45213	6453	1.14
S ₁ N ₂	65200	48253	16947	1.35
S ₁ N ₃	82066	51293	30773	1.60
S ₁ N ₄	93334	54333	39001	1.72
S ₁ N ₅	96000	57373	38627	1.67
S ₂ N ₁	58000	45813	12187	1.27
S ₂ N ₂	79334	48853	30481	1.62
S ₂ N ₃	87834	51893	35941	1.69
S ₂ N ₄	99846	54933	44913	1.82
S ₂ N ₅	102160	57973	44187	1.76
S ₃ N ₁	60666	46413	14253	1.31
S ₃ N ₂	83334	49453	33881	1.69
S ₃ N ₃	94000	52493	41507	1.79
S ₃ N ₄	107840	55533	52307	1.94
S ₃ N ₅	109334	58573	50761	1.87